

BEST PRACTICES FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF CRYPTOSPORIDIOSIS ON DAIRY FARMS

A HANDBOOK FOR FARM MANAGERS

Cryptosporidiosis, a parasitic infection best tackled by prevention

Cryptosporidiosis is a **parasitic, zoonotic** (can affect both animals and humans) **disease** caused by protozoa of the *Cryptosporidium* genus. Infected individuals are capable of excreting millions to billions of infectious oocysts daily. In bovines, under experimental conditions, only 17 oocysts are necessary to make a calf sick, and a sick calf sheds millions of oocyst in its faeces. These oocysts are very resistant in the environment. **Direct transmission of *Cryptosporidium*, through oocysts ingestion, is the most common form of transmission.** This occurs via the fecal-oral route from infected hosts, including animal-to-animal, animal-to-human, human-to-animal, and human-to-human transmissions. Contamination can also be by water. YOPs (Young Old Pregnant Immunocompromised People) are particularly vulnerable to *Cryptosporidium* infections.

Several subspecies of *Cryptosporidium* can be hosted by bovines but the main agent of disease in (young) bovines is ***Cryptosporidium parvum***, it is considered **endemic** (consistently present on farms). Clinical signs can range from a **mild to inapparent infection in older animals to severe scouring in young animals**, and can cause varying degrees of dehydration, dullness, anorexia, fever and loss of body condition. In bovines, animals considered the most vulnerable are young and immunocompromised individuals. **Calves between 0 to 3 weeks of age can be vulnerable** if they did not receive a good colostrum protection. Furthermore, the colostrum protection does not protect calves against *Cryptosporidium* specifically. Even though the economic impact of *Cryptosporidium* on bovine farms is not well known yet it is expected that it **contributes a lot to direct and indirect costs on farm** through veterinary and care costs, labor costs, mortality or production losses such as reduced growth in young animals.

There are currently no vaccines available to prevent cryptosporidiosis and only a few medical treatments. The best way to reduce the impact of *Cryptosporidium* on farms is **prevention.**

This handbook presents a set of best practices for the management of cryptosporidiosis on dairy farms.

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MANAGEMENT OF CALVING PLACE

Ideally, **calving should always take place in an individual pen dedicated to calving**. To limit stress, the cow should not be put in the calving pen too early and should be able to maintain visual contact with the herd.

The calving place is the first potential place where calves can be infected after birth. Fresh calves are very vulnerable to pathogens meaning that the **calving place needs to be as clean as possible**. Ideally the floor of the calving box should be a non-slip mat easy to clean with wood shavings. If possible, clean and disinfect the pen after each calving. Before adding straw, some chalk can be spread on the floor.

If the cows calve in group pens, it is important to keep the pen as clean as possible and to avoid overstocking. It is necessary to have a separate sickbay where infected cows can be segregated as infected cows can very easily infect their calf or other mothers and their calves through manure or contact. To minimise the risk of infection, calves should be removed from the calving pen as soon as possible after birth.

When the cows calve in a pen with straw, it's not always possible to renew the straw, but a fresh layer of straw should be added before each calving. When the litter is removed, the same steps should be followed as when cleaning the individual calf pens to remove as many pathogens as possible. When the cows calve on a mat, the mat should be thoroughly cleaned (and disinfected) after each calving.

- Ideally, calving should always take place in an individual pen dedicated to calving
- Hygiene of the calving location is important as it is a potential location of contamination of the newborn calf
- The calving box should never be used as a sickbay

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COLOSTRUM AND CALF IMMUNITY

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2.1 IMPORTANCE OF CALVES IMMUNITY

Calves are born without any acquired immunity from their mothers. The calf builds up passive immunity by absorbing the antibodies contained in colostrum. An immunity gap is created around 2-3 weeks of age when the passive immunity from the

colostrum decreases and the active immunity of the calf is not yet achieved (Figure 1). The immune system is effective but it takes time (more than 3 weeks) to produce adequate antibody levels.

Figure 1: Passive immunity, active immunity of the calf and high risk period for cryptosporidiosis

Cryptosporidiosis happens mostly before the calf has developed an active immunity. There is no colostrum protection against the cryptosporidiosis. Several other

pathogens can cause diarrhoea in young calves (Figure 2). Very often a combination of pathogens can be found, for instance *Cryptosporidium* and Rotavirus.

Figure 2: Some sources of bovine diarrhoea according to the age of calves

2.2 COLOSTRUM

2.2.1 Amount of colostrum

It is very important that a calf **receives sufficient colostrum of good quality**. Colostrum is unique and indispensable as the calf's first food. It contains antibodies, live immune cells, minerals, hormones, signalling agents, energy and building blocks.

A good rule of thumb for colostrum management are the **5Q** Quantity, **Q**uick, **Q**uantified, **Q**uality, **sQ**ueaky clean. It can also be expressed as **plenty, quick, frequently, fresh and of good quality**. If these actions are performed properly, colostrum management on the dairy farm is optimal.

The ideal is to have the calf drink at least sufficient quantity, depending of the quality of colostrum (Table 1) within 6 hours of birth.

> **Quantity**= a quantity adapted to the quality of the colostrum (Table 1)

> **Quick** = within 1 hour after birth

> **Frequently** = a second colostrum intake within 12 to 24h after birth

> **Quantified** = the quantity of IgG is evaluated

> **Quality** = min 22 brix

> **SQueaky clean** = Colostrum and colostrum distribution devices should be clean

2.2.2 Colostrum quality

The colostrum provided to the calf should always be of good quality. Therefore it is important to **test colostrum for its quality**. Especially for colostrum that will be frozen to include in a colostrum bank. The quality of colostrum can be checked with several methods. One of them is with a **refractometer**. A refractometer measures the optical density of the colostrum and is expressed in brix. This brix value indicates how thick the colostrum is. The denser the colostrum structure, the more antibodies or IgG molecules are present in the colostrum. Another way

to test the colostrum quality is with a **density meter**. This method has as downside that it's temperature dependent, while a refractometer isn't.

Recent research advises to give calves at least **300g IgG** (instead of the 220g which was advised previously), and this preferably within the first hour of life. This to prevent calves from getting sick. The previous recommendation was to reduce the risk of calves dying. The volume of colostrum a newborn calf should intake must therefore be adapted according to the quality of the colostrum, using the following table (Table 1)

% Brix	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
IgG(g/l)	0	12	24	35	47	58	70	82	93	105	116	128	139	150	162
Colostrum Volume (220g IgG)	see roadmap below table				5	4	3,5	3	2,5	2,5	2	2	2	2	2
Colostrum Volume (300g IgG)	see roadmap below table				6,5	5,5	4,5	4	3,5	3	3	2,5	2,5	2	2

Table 1: Minimum volume of colostrum to provide according to Brix and IgG value. Correspondance between the Brix value (%), the approximate quantity of IgG in the colostrum (in g/l) and the volume of colostrum to provide to reach 220g of IgG (rounded for the upper 1/2 and with a maximum of 4 liters). The volume to give is not an objective but a minimum.

Roadmap :

- 1 If occasionally that the colostrum quality is inadequate (less than 22 brix), then you have following options
 - a. Give a part of the colostrum from the own mother but complete with good quality colostrum from another cow on the farm
 - b. Give good quality colostrum from another cow (preferably from the own farm) from the colostrum bank
 - c. Give colostrum replacer whith good quality and a sufficient amount of IgG
- 2 If the colostrum quality is regularly inadequate (less than 22 brix), then it's strongly advised to have a look at the general dry cow management and the colostrum collection with your adviser since this has a big influence on general colostrum quality.
 - a. Ration (protein content at least 12% in last weeks before calving, mineral and vitamin status, dry matter uptake (preferably 12kg dry matter at least))
 - b. Length of the dry period (at least 35 days)

c. Timing of the first milking after calving (preferably within 1 hour after calving)

d. Method of colostrum collection (no dilution because of flushing in milking robots).

Colostrum is of good quality if it has a brix value of 22 or higher. If a cow produces better quality colostrum than needed for the calf, it is possible to freeze it. This way, it can later be used to give to a calf whose mother produces not enough colostrum or too low-quality colostrum. Another option is to ask another farmer for colostrum or buying colostrum from a colostrum bank. If the quality of colostrum is good, choose fresh colostrum from the mother. If not, add good quality colostrum from the colostrum bank to the colostrum of the mother...

2.2.3 Preparation of colostrum for colostrum bank

It is possible to pasteurize fresh colostrum before freezing to eliminate bacteria (ex: paratuberculosis) at 60°C for 1 hour. This doesn't destroy all the pathogens, only 95% and might destroy part of the IgG.

Freezing also destroys white blood cells, but if there are certain bacteria like paratuberculosis, mycoplasma, salmonella... present on the farm, the advantages outweigh the disadvantages.

It is best to **freeze colostrum as soon as possible** and in small portions so that it can be quickly thawed again. Freezing colostrum in bags can also speed up the process because it involves a larger surface area, which makes defrosting faster. Colostrum should not be thawed using a microwave. Use a milk warmer.

The temperature of the water should not exceed 55-60°C in order to not destroy antibodies. If defrosting is slow, bacteria multiply and partly inhibit antibodies absorption.

If you do not want to freeze colostrum, **fresh colostrum can be kept in a refrigerator** up to 5 days for non-pasteurized and up to 7 days for pasteurized colostrum.

If you freeze colostrum in small portions, they can also be given the first 14 days of life in the milk to provide the calf with additional local antibodies in the gut. If it's good quality colostrum (22brix or higher) then 50ml twice a day suffice. If it's lower quality (less than 22 brix) then you need to add 100ml twice a day.

2.2.4. Time of distribution

It is important that the calf drinks colostrum as soon as possible. You should ensure that all calves receive a quantity of colostrum adapted to the quality of the colostrum (Table 1) within 6 hours. These goals are important because the cow's colostrum contains the most antibodies immediately after calving and the calf's capacity to absorb them into their blood is at the highest. Thus, the **cow must be milked as soon as possible after calving**, because the colostrum quality starts to gradually decline after calving (Table 2). In addition, the calf's intestines can absorb the most antibodies in the first 4 hours after birth. The

antibodies are absorbed via IgG receptors. After 4 hours, the number of IgG receptors in the intestinal wall drops sharply and it is more difficult for the calf to absorb sufficient antibodies. The absorption capacity gradually decreases and **24 hours after the birth of the calf, there is no absorption of antibodies from colostrum** possible at all (Table 2). Colostrum is not only important because of the antibodies it contains. It also has a protective effect in the intestines of the calf. Colostrum supports and stimulates the production of new intestinal wall cells. Therefore, it is good to give the calf colostrum for the first 3 days of its life to protect the intestine and to provide local antibodies that remain in the gut. quantity is drunk.

Antibody content in colostrum after calving				
Moment of milking	Directly	6 hours	10 hours	14 hours
Level of antibodies	100 %	83 %	73 %	67 %
Absorption capacity of antibodies by the calf's intestinal wall cells				
Moment of intake	Immediately after birth	After 6 hours	After 8 hours	After 24 hours
Level of antibodies	100 %	50 %	33 %	0 %

Table 2: Importance of timing of colostrum milking and intake

2.2.5. Temperature of distribution

The temperature at which colostrum is provided to the calf must be close to the physiological temperature (during suckling) approx 38°C. Besides it improves the digestibility of fat when provided at body temperature.

2.2.6. Type of distribution

There are 3 main types of colostrum distribution:

- > With a Bottle (sometimes only possible for max 3 litres depending on the calf)
- > Drench
- > Directly from the mother (in that case it is not possible to evaluate the intake)

Bottle or drench are preferred to make sure sufficient quantity is drunk.

- A good colostrum intake is essential to the calf's resistance against infections
- Quantity and quick = a quantity adapted to the quality of colostrum (Table 1) within 6 hours after birth
- Frequently = a second colostrum intake within 12 to 24h after birth
- Quality colostrum = min 22 brix
- Fresh colostrum = if possible but if not, use good quality colostrum from the colostrum bank

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AVOIDING UMBILICAL INFECTIONS

Besides the immunity provided by the colostrum, there is another important step that needs to be taken to protect the newborn calf against pathogens. Meaning the disinfection from the umbilicus as a calf with an umbilical infection is much more sensitive for other infections.

This can be done with iodine tincture or Chlorexhidine. It disinfects and dries out the umbilical cord preventing pathogens from entering the calf's bloodstream. The cup used for dipping should be clean and hands (or gloves) should be washed. Empty wharton jelly (gelatinous substance within the umbilical cord) so the umbilical cord dries better and continue disinfection until complete dry.

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MANAGEMENT OF CALF HOUSING

The following points regarding housing of young cattle are very important in reducing *Cryptosporidium* contamination. The most important point regarding housing is hygiene. ***Cryptosporidium* (oocysts) can survive for 3-4 months in the environment.** Cryptosporidiosis occurs when calves have low immunity and there is a high *Cryptosporidium* pressure. Therefore it is very important to reduce the *Cryptosporidium* presence (number of oocysts in

the environment) with **good cleaning/disinfections procedures** and **enough individual housing for calves** (if individual housed, then the number of calf places should be 15% of the number of cows) or **low stocking density**.

4.1 CLEANING AND DISINFECTION

It's very important to **clean the individual calf pens between every calf** to reduce the build-up of infectious agents like *Cryptosporidium* in the environment. A good cleaning protocol consists of multiple steps and is combined with disinfection. The different steps will be explained in more detail below. When you clean with a high pressure cleaner, no other calves must be present in the environment, especially if you clean inside a building so they cannot come into contact with aerosols from the cleaning process and the operator should wear a protective mask. If possible use an all-in/all-out system. The steps below describe the process to clean the pens/hutches, but it's recommended to use the same steps for water, feed and milk bowls.

1 Stripping (removal of organic materials like litter and waste). The first step is the 'dry' removal of all the organic material, not only from the pens or hutches but also from the environment where the pen/hutch stands. This is necessary to assure that the cleaning product comes into contact with the surface of the pen/hutch instead of organic material and that it doesn't get deactivated because of the organic material.

2 Use of a cleaning agent (foaming): read carefully the instructions before use in order to use the right concentration and contact time. Concentration and contact time to be used are usually higher for *Cryptosporidium* than for other pathogens. Make sure that the cleaning agent is active against *Cryptosporidium* oocysts (ex: Kenosan© (foam)).

Use a high pressure cleaner with a foam gun to spread the cleaning agent evenly over the surface of the hutch/pen you want to clean.

3 Wait 30 minutes or more before you go to the next step so the cleaning agent can do its work. The duration might depend of the cleaning agent. Follow the instructions on duration of application.

4 Clean the pen/hutch with a high pressure cleaner/ steam cleaner. Make sure to remove all visible dirt. If there are still other calves present in the same stable, house them temporary somewhere else while you are cleaning, because you can spread the germs in the air with the pressure cleaner.

5 Let the pen/hutch dry till it's completely dry. Do this in the sun if possible, since the UV-rays are a natural disinfectant. In case of igloo's put them on their back so that the inside can be reached by the sunlight (Figure 3).

Figure 3:
Cleaning of
folded calf
pen

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6 Disinfect using a hydrogen peroxide-based disinfectant or quaternary ammonia-based products (ex: Kenocox®, Dekoksane®, Prophyl-s®). These disinfectants are efficient against *Cryptosporidium*. Other disinfectants can also be used depending on which infectious agents are present. Bleach or cresyl are not advised as they are not efficient against *Cryptosporidium*.

Best is to alternate between two agents with a different spectrum of action if you don't use a broad spectrum agent. Read carefully the instructions before use in order to use the right concentration and contact time. The contact time required can be quite long. If necessary repeat the disinfection step if the disinfection product dries to fast.

These disinfectants are hazardous to the operator and precautions need to be taken including the use of personal protective equipment for the operator, for example face masks

7 Let them dry and implement a sanitary emptying period. For *Cryptosporidium* natural disinfection period would mean leaving calf pens empty for at least 3-4 months. On farm this isn't often possible, but try to have enough hutches/pens so you can have at least a

3-week period for leaving calf accommodation empty. Empty periods are one of the most important hygienic actions against diseases because many pathogens die without moisture and heat from an animal nearby.

8 In case of water, milk and food bowls: rinse them carefully after disinfection before you use them for a new calf. Hutches/pens don't need to be rinsed (to remove the rest of disinfectant) before use.

9 Put some chalk on the floor of the hutch/pen before use. Unextinguished chalk has a pH increasing effect and therefore a strong effect in absorbing water and killing bacteria. The best method is to sprinkle the boxes 1 to 2 days after cleaning and then leave them empty for 2 to 3 weeks. This way the chalk can work properly, and the calf will not be bothered by it. Always add a thick layer of straw before the introduction of a new calf into the pen. Chalk can be irritant so always scatter with gloves and be careful not to inhale the dust. This chalk is absolutely not suitable for use in cow cubicles! Due to the increasing PH, cows may get burn marks on the udders. Ordinary chalk can also be used to sprinkle in the calf pens but has a slightly less bactericidal effect.

4.2 BEDDING

Calves always need to lie dry. A calf loses a lot of heat due to wet bedding and can (re)infect itself if it comes into contact with faeces. Compensating for this loss of heat costs a lot of energy. Energy that the calf can no longer use to grow or maintain its resistance. Therefore, **dry straw bed** is very important for the growth and health of a calf. A good way to see

if there is enough straw in the calf pen is the nesting score. The score can be determined by looking at the calf's legs. If the calf is lying in the straw and the legs are no longer visible, then there is enough straw in the calf pen (Nest score 3, Figure 4). Another test is the knee test, when you kneel in the bedding of the calf, your knees need to stay dry.

Nest score 1 : Legs fully visible

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Nest score 2 : Legs half visible

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Nest score 3 : Legs not visible

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Figure 4: Bedding in calf pens (adapted from vetvice/cowsignals)

4.3 PLACEMENT OF CALF PENS

When housing calves in hutches, their placement should be considered carefully. They need to be positioned so that the calves do not undergo negative effects from the weather and when it rains, no manure from other calves flows into their hutch. Because this can cause the spreading of pathogens between calves.

If you use hutches place them on a concrete floor with a slope and a gutter so that the manure cannot reach other calves. It is best to place them with the front at the opposite of the prevailing wind so that the calves have the least impact of the wind. In summer sometimes it's better to place them with the opening

towards the northeast to minimize the warmth from the sun. Calves less than 14 days old are best housed somewhere separate from the older calves. This will prevent the older calves from infecting the younger calves that have a weaker immunity.

Calves that will be sold are best housed somewhere close to the entrance of the farm and separate from the other calves that will be raised on the farm to avoid that the merchant introduces other pathogens on the farm. If you cannot house them somewhere separately, provide boots for the merchant.

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4.4 AGE OF MOVEMENT

It is best to house the calf individually for at least 14 days. This will give the calf enough opportunity to build up sufficient immunity to better withstand the transition into group housing. All calves (even in individual housing) should nevertheless have a visual and physical contact with at least one other bovine. Some calves can be housed individually without physical contacts only if justified by high prevalence of diseases in calves. It can be advised to house the calves with *Cryptosporidium* outside so that they do not contaminate the other calves (calves can be tested for positivity for *Cryptosporidium*, see section 10). If the sanitary conditions are very good

on the farm, the calves can be housed collectively (by pair or more) from the day of birth.

In group housing, it is good to use an all-in-all-out system. This means that a group of calves of about the same age are housed together and move together. Preferably, the age difference is not more than 3 weeks. If the group is moved to a new pen, the composition of the group will not change, and no new animals will be added. Therefore, the infection pressure will remain lower. In addition, it is good to make the groups not bigger than 6 to 8 calves.

4.5 CALF HOUSING MATERIAL

The housing material should be easy to clean and dry after cleaning. It is therefore better to choose plastic (or polyester) calf pens rather than, for example, wood. It can also be an advantage if the calf pens are movable. Boxes that are normally kept inside can be cleaned outside and dried in the sun. This allows dairy farmers to avoid leaving bedding inside with the other calves. Another point of interest is the numbering of the teat buckets. This ensures that each calf has its own bucket and no germs can be transmitted through the teat buckets.

- Clean and disinfect pens/hutches and other calf material following the right protocol and use cleaning and disinfection agents that work against *Cryptosporidium*. Respect the instructions on the labels.
- Additional bedding must be regularly added so calves always lay dry in a deep bed of straw (nesting score, knee test)
- Place hutches/pens logically to avoid spreading of germs, possible contamination via merchants.
- When buying new pens/ hutches, make sure they can be cleaned easily (smooth surfaces, movable,...)
- Take precautions when it's cold to keep the fresh calves warm.

4.6 ENVIRONMENTAL TEMPERATURE

A calf has an increased cold limit especially in the first few days of life. The cold limit means that below this limit the calf consumes energy to stay warm. The older the calf gets the lower the cold limit becomes. This is because the calf starts to eat more and more solid feed. The rumen produces heat in the process. So, the more solid feed the calf eats, the more heat it

produces. If the environmental temperature is below 10 °C, it is best for the calf to wear a calf jacket (Figure 5), both if you use inside or outside housing. This allows the calf to better utilize its energy on growth and immunity rather than keeping its body warm and prevents the calve from slowing down its digestion.

Figure 5:
Young calf
wearing a
jacket

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CALF NUTRITION

5.1 MILK

A calf needs adequate and qualitative nutrition. The calf uses this to grow, for the immune system development, maintenance and resistance to stress. You can use whole milk as well as milk replacer but discarded milk should be avoided because this can cause the calf to get diarrhoea as well as antimicrobial resistance. Milk with antibiotics and with too many cells are forbidden. Fresh calving

cows milk is difficult to digest. Calves appreciate regularity in milk composition, temperature and distribution schedule. During the 1st week of age of calves it is possible to add 50-100ml of colostrum in calves' milk for a local protection of the gut.

5.1.1. Milk temperature at distribution

The temperature of the milk, when it reaches the calf, should not be too cold. A young calf spends a lot of energy staying warm. If the calf drinks milk that is

too cold, the digestibility of fatty matter is decreased. The ideal drinking temperature of milk is between 38 and 40 degrees Celsius. Only if you feed ad lib milk then the temperature can be lower, but no lower than 20 degrees.

5.1.2. Preparation of milk powder

A week-old calf needs at least 1 kg dry matter of milk or milk powder per day. Whole milk contains 12.5 -13.5 % dry matter. In the first week portions should not be higher than 2-2,5 litres of milk at a time. Between 1 and 2 weeks portions are maximum 2.5-3 litres of milk at a time. Calves can also be fed acidified milk without limit. The pH of the milk should then be below 5 and the milk should be offered cold (+-20°C) to the calf. Feeding acidified milk has a positive effect on intestinal health. In doing so, calves can drink unlimited amounts of milk, which will help them grow faster.

litre of milk. To avoid digestive disorders the regularity in the composition, preparation and distribution of the milk replacer is important. The density of the milk replacer must be adapted according to the breed of the calf (ex: 11% brix for Holstein, 12-14% brix for crossbred, 15% brix for Jersiaise) and the season (+1% brix if the temperature of the environment is below 10°C). In addition, it is good to discuss with the young animal specialist what the goals are in terms of growth and health of the calf. This allows a farm-specific approach to be made.

The way the milk replacer is prepared is important for the final concentration of milk powder in the milk. Therefore, great care must be taken to ensure that the milk is prepared according to the label. The minimal concentration is 125g of milk replacer combined with 875g of water to create 1 litre of milk replacer. But the recommended concentration is 150g milk replacer per

If you use milk replacer, then it's very important to use drinkable water (public water). Calves are very sensitive and bad water quality can cause diarrhoea and can be a source of contamination by *Cryptosporidium*.

The temperature of the water used to prepare the milk replacer must follow the indications given for the specific milk powder.

5.2 DISTRIBUTION OF MILK AND WATER

Offering water to a calf is possible from first day of life. If solid food is offered, water is compulsory. Milk goes directly into the abomasum thanks to oesophageal groove whereas water goes into the rumen. If there is no water, solid feed ferment in the rumen.

Ideally, the calf should drink the water from a bucket in a low position and the milk from a teat bucket in a high position (Figure 6). If the calf drinks water from a teat bucket, the water temperature should be not too high. Water is best offered at least 1 hour after the milk has been offered as, if large quantities are drunk, there is a risk that water will dilute the milk in the abomasum and this reduces the coagulation of milk.

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Figure 6: A pen with milk (teat bucket), water (bucket) and solid feed (in the hut) distribution devices

The oesophageal groove closes when calves are drinking milk or when they are very thirsty (Figure 7). This reflex is triggered by various stimuli, such as consistency, temperature, sucking on a teat and a high head position. When this reflex doesn't work properly (happens often when calves are young) or the calf gets too big milk portions in the first weeks after birth, then the milk can end up in the rumen and ferment.

Feed and water, esophageal slit open

Milk esophageal slit closed

Figure 7: Functioning of oesophageal slit/groove (source: Cow signals)

When a calf has diarrhoea, it can more easily replenish the fluid it loses due to the diarrhoea itself if it has access to a bucket of water. A calf with severe diarrhoea can easily become dehydrated if it does not get enough fluids. Calf can lose 20% of its body weight. With milk alone, a calf can only just supplement this loss of moisture, and it has nothing left to grow from. If a calf does not yet have diarrhoea

but starts drinking more water, it can be an indication that the calf is going to develop diarrhoea. As a result, an empty bucket can be a good indicator that the calf needs to be monitored. If a calf has access to solid feed, it is important that it also has access to water. This is because water is needed for proper rumen development and digestion of the solid feed.

5.3 SOLID FEED

The calf has the need to eat solid feed from a very young age. It is possible to offer solid feed to the calf from the first week of a calf's life. A handful of muesli or solid feed is already enough to introduce the calf to solid feed. The calf will not eat much solid feed at first, but it can get used to the structure and the way the feed is provided. This will help the calf make a better transition to group housing. A calf experiences less stress if there is only one change at a time. The rumen will develop into a well-functioning organ in 3 weeks if it consumes 100-150 g of solid feed per day. A calf will start ruminating when it is three weeks old. In the third week of life a well-fed calf can already eat 0.5 kg of solid feed and in the fourth week 1 kg. This is about 20% of the total energy intake. The solid feed should contain sufficient energy, protein and

structure. In addition, it is a source of vitamins and minerals. Roughage and a good rumen fermentation are necessary for the health of the forestomachs and intestines.

- Calves should be provided milk, solid feed and water
- Feeding discarded milk must be avoided
- Respect the recommended concentration and temperature for milk powder preparation and distribution
- 3 distribution systems should be available: one teat bucket for milk, one bucket for water or individual water nipples, one solid feed distribution device (Figure 6).

SICK CALVES MANAGEMENT

6.1 USE OF SICKBAY

When calves are housed in collective housing, sick calves should be taken out of the group and isolated from the other calves. The isolation of sick calves should be maintained until one week after they stop showing signs of diarrhoea as they are still very likely to spread high numbers of oocysts. A proper sickbay should be used when possible. It is a separated pen without physical contact with other calves (to avoid contamination of neighbouring calves), if possible, in a separate room. It provides clean straw bedding for the thermal comfort of the calf and permanent

access to clean water. Pens should be spaced far enough from each other to assure that no fluids can go from one calf to another (0,5-1m).

When calves are sick, it's an important rule of thumb **to first take care of the healthy calves before going to the sick ones** to minimize the risk of spreading pathogens. Also, the youngest calves should be nurtured before the older ones. Boots and hands should be cleaned between sick calves and other animals.

6.2 TREATMENTS

6.2.1. General care of calves with (*Cryptosporidium*) diarrhoea

Nursing is the key to the success of the treatment of diarrheic calves: isolate the sick calf, maintain a comfortable temperature, regularly change the straw bedding, assess the calves 3 times a day, rehydrate it. The treatment of symptoms relies mostly on rehydration of the calf, orally or if necessary through

venous path and intestinal patches.

When a calf has diarrhoea, one of the first steps is to prevent dehydration. This can be done by providing electrolytes. Give them in multiple small portions a day because calves with diarrhoea lose a lot of fluid (at least 6 litre of electrolytes). Make sure you

- use qualitative electrolytes that also help prevent acidosis. Quantitative electrolytes don't contain sodium bicarbonate or dextrose, but preferably propionate, acetate as deacidifiers and glucose, lactose as energy source.

- Besides electrolytes a calf can also be given antispasmodics, mucilage, activated charcoal, essential

oils and cider vinegar (ex. Carbogel®, Obionekk®).

Probiotics can be given for prevention of gastrointestinal disorders and to make a barrier flora at birth or reconstitute it after a diarrheic episode.

6.2.2. Specific treatments used against *Cryptosporidium*

- Before starting a treatment, it is necessary to assess the state of the calf: temperature, liveliness, apathy, appetite, decubitus position, suckling reflex, dehydration (skin fold, eye depression), colour of the eye conjunctive, palpation of the umbilicus and joints...

In case of an outbreak, the search for pathogen agents is compulsory.

HALUFOGINONE

Halofuginone lactate can only be given as a preventive treatment in farms with a *Cryptosporidium parvum* detection history. It is a Cryptosporidiostatic that prevents the proliferation of the parasite without killing it. It reduces the excretion of oocysts and the intensity of diarrhoea. It can be used at the beginning of a diarrhoea episode (24h). **If the diarrhoea already started then Halofuginone lactate should not be used**

because its toxicity in combination with a damaged gut wall. It should not be given to a calf with an empty stomach but with milk or a rehydration solution. Ideally the calf should be weighted beforehand to precisely evaluate its weight. The treatment must be given for 7 consecutive days. To avoid the contact with the skin, gloves should be worn.

PAROMOMYCIN

Paromomycin is not registered for use against *Cryptosporidium* in Belgium and the Netherlands, but off label it can be used under strict regulations, which differ in each country (Table 3). This can be given as curative treatment on farms with severe problems.

Paromomycin is an antiobiotic so only curative. A confirmed diagnosis of Cryptosporidiosis is required before treatment can commence. The treatment must be given for 5 to 7 consecutive days. Due to its nephrotoxic effect, this antibiotic should not be given to dehydrated calves. As for any other antibiotic, the risk of the development of an antibiotic resistance must be taken into account, especially when it is administered orally.

	Belgium	France	The Netherlands	United Kingdom
Halofuginon Commercial names	Halocur®, Kriptazen®, Halagon®, Halofusol®	Halocur®, Kriptazen®, Halagon®, Halofusol®, Stenorolcrypto®	Kriptazen®, Halagon®, Halofusol®, Stenorolcrypto®, Cryptisel®	Halocur®, Kriptazen®, Halagon®, Halofusol®, Stenorolcrypto®, Cryptisel®
Paromomycin Autorisation and commercial names	Not registered for use against <i>Cryptosporidium</i> , but off label can be used under strict regulations (Parofor®, Gabbrovet®)	Only curative Newly authorised for <i>Cryptosporidium</i> (only Gabbrovet multi®) against <i>E.Coli</i> and <i>Cryptosporidium</i>	Not registered for use against <i>Cryptosporidium</i> , but off label can be used under strict regulations (Parofor®, Gabbrovet®, Gabbrovet multi®)	Authorised against <i>Cryptosporidium</i> (Gabbrovet Multi®, Parofor® <i>Cryptosporidium</i>)

Table 3: Use of treatment against *Cryptosporidium* in the 4 countries of the H4DC project (information valid in January 2023)

- Sick calves should be isolated
- Good nursing (temperature, bedding) is essential for recovery
- Calves with diarrhoea must be well rehydrated
- In case of an outbreak, the search for pathogen agents for diarrhoea is compulsory
- Halofuginone is used as a preventive treatment
- Paromomycin is used as a curative treatment

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VACCINATION OF COWS

By having the cow vaccinated against rotavirus, coronavirus and *E. coli*, the cow will produce antibodies against these pathogens. These antibodies will also be present in the colostrum. When the calf drinks the colostrum, it will ingest the antibodies against these pathogens and thus be protected from the diseases they cause. This will only be the case if the calf receives the colostrum in the first hours after birth when it can still absorb the antibodies in the intestine. If the calf gets *Cryptosporidium* and at the same time suffers from other pathogens such as

coronavirus, rotavirus or *E. coli* then the symptoms of the disease are generally more severe. By protecting the calf from the other diseases, it has a better chance of fighting *Cryptosporidium* itself.

- The vaccination of mothers permits to produce a colostrum enriched with antibodies against some agents responsible for calves diarrhoea (Rotavirus, Coronavirus, *E. coli*)

8

DRY COW MANAGEMENT

The dry period of the cow is very important for the production of colostrum. A cow needs 5 to 6 weeks of dry maternity to produce enough litres of good quality colostrum. For primiparous cows, the aim is even to have a dry period of 8 weeks. During this dry period the cow's ration is important for the development of the calf and the production of the colostrum. A good dry period ration contains 12-14% crude protein and 830 net energy per kg dry matter (920 net energy in close up dry period if it is separated in two periods). In addition, minerals, vitamins (Vit E) and trace elements (Se) in the ration are important for the immunity system of the cow and the calf and the development of the calf's intestines. If the intestine of

the calf are not well developed, it cannot absorb the antibodies from the colostrum properly.

It is important to have a good management of parasitism. Even if the literature on the topic is scarce, it is commonly accepted that a parasitic infestation (for instance by *Fasciola hepatica*) can affect the quality of colostrum (via parasitic spoliation) and reduce the ability of the cow to produce colostrum antibodies against calves' neonatal diseases.

- A good management of the dry period of cows (duration and ration) will permit a good development of the unborn calf and a good onset of the lactation

OTHER BIOSECURITY MEASURES

At minimum these general biosecurity measure should be applied:

- > Take care of the healthy animals before sick animals (and start with the youngest ones, go from the youngest to the oldest calves).
- > Sickbay : use of specific clothing, wash boots, wash hands before and after contact with diseased animals, use specific material only to be used in sickbay.
- > Try to go into as few pens as possible because you can spread pathogens between calves with your boots.
- > Don't allow strangers within the calf stable more than necessary.

> Clean boots before going into the calf stable. Ideally clothes (overalls) should be changed as they can spread pathogens.

> Quarantine for introduced animals: It is advised that in the case of an introduction of new animals (young or adults) in the farm they should be put in quarantine for 3 weeks before being introduced in the herd.

Each farm should refer to the national recommendation for biosecurity measures of its country.

- Good biosecurity measures are set to reduce the risk of introduction of pathogens in the farm, limit the spreading of pathogens between animals in the farm and the risk of contamination of humans

TESTS FOR THE PRESENCE OF *CRYPTOSPORIDIUM*

Quick tests, at the calf's bedside, can be used to confirm the presence of *Cryptosporidium* oocysts on samples of feces of diarrreic calves.

Some strip tests (example in Figure 8) allow to search simultaneously of faecal antigens of rotavirus, coronavirus, *E. coli* K99 and CS31A, *Clostridium perfringens* or *Giardia* (a flagellate protozoa). It is frequent to detect *Cryptosporidium* at the same time as several other neonatal gastroenteritis agents. Accurate diagnosis is important for a good management of disease. As, for instance, for cryptosporidiosis, a confirmed diagnosis, is needed before a treatment (Halofuginone or Paromomycin) can commence.

- Different tests to assess the presence of *Cryptosporidium* exist. Your vet will be able to use tests and detection kits available in your country to establish his diagnosis and suggest adapted presentation and/or treatment

Figure 8: Example of strip tests for the detection of faecal antigens for several agents of diarrhoea

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APPENDIX 1

SUMMARY OF RISK FACTORS FOR THE CONTAMINATION OF CALVES FROM 0 TO 3 WEEKS

Transmission Pathway	Critical Control Point	Proposed Critical Limits and Recommendations
Vertical	Calf feeding directly from Mum	Clean cow's udders with harmless-to-calf mild antimicrobial agent prior to calf taking colostrum (Peek & Divers, 2017).
Vertical / Horizontal	Calf in direct contact with dam/adult manure	Ensure that in the days prior to birth, dams are kept separated from young/neonate calves (Faubert & Litvinsky, 2000).
Horizontal	Contact with non-farm based humans e.g. vets, contractors, commercial representatives	<p>Visits/animal contact by people based off-site from the farm should only occur when strictly necessary. Especially minimize their contact with youngest/most vulnerable animals (Brennan & Christley, 2008).</p> <p>Use appropriate biosecurity measures (e.g. foot dips, sterilised equipment if reused) (Brennan & Christley, 2012).</p>
Horizontal	Direct contact with other calves (some contact is necessary for welfare reasons)	<p>Housing neonate calves in group or individual housing was unrelated to risk of <i>Cryptosporidium parvum</i> illness (Brainard et al. 2020).</p> <p>House calves by age and avoid movement between groups and housing areas (Brainard et al. 2020), especially calves <3 weeks (Silverlås et al. 2009).</p>
Environmental	Indirect contact with manure of other calves either between housing or via fomites e.g. shovels, buckets, wheelbarrows etc.	<p>Regularly remove old bedding and feces and empty housing between single/groups of calves (Brainard et al. 2020).</p> <p>Low pressure (< 70 bar) washing rather than spray oocysts widely. Pressure washing may both increase (Hancock-Alleb et al. 2017) and decrease (Piva et al. 2016; Smith et al. 2021) transmission of <i>Cryptosporidium parvum</i>. Drying surfaces after pressure washing and applying a surface anti-microbial may reduce transmission (Kihlstrom et al. 2001).</p> <p>Use same equipment for a single-age/place cohort. Wash or disinfect items that must move between areas (e.g. calfcart wheels, Pasture.io, 2021).</p>
Environmental / Vector-borne	Contact with farm workers and their clothing	<p>When entry to calf housing is unavoidable,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) wash hands (Gormley et al., 2011); ii) change clothing; iii) use disposable shoe covers and iv) use disposable equipment or disinfect equipment (Pasture.io, 2021). <p>These steps are particularly important when moving to care for animals in another area or age group.</p>
Vector-borne	Contact with (passive) mechanical transfer insect vectors e.g. flies or non-insect host e.g. mouse, rat etc.	<p>Flies can convey oocysts (Graczyk et al. 2004). Clean spaces where flies might shelter and breed. Increased resistance to insecticides and difficulty of preventing insecticide ingress to milk products also makes physical environment management desirable (Machtinger et al. 2021).</p> <p><i>Cryptosporidium parvum</i> infection is more likely in calves during hot and humid weather (Brainard et al., 2020) so take action early in the fly season to reduce numbers later.</p> <p>Undertake vermin control measures such as removing vermin breeding spaces and reducing vermin access to food sources on premises (AHDB 2023).</p>

APPENDIX 1

SUMMARY OF RISK FACTORS FOR THE CONTAMINATION OF CALVES FROM 0 TO 3 WEEKS

Transmission Pathway	Critical Control Point	Proposed Critical Limits and Recommendations
Food and ingested water contamination	Calf given fecally-contaminated colostrum or milk (frozen)	Correctly thaw milk or colostrum. No type of artificial feeding mechanism (bucket, teat, tube, etc.) has a consistent association with higher risk (Brainard et al. 2020).
Food and ingested water contamination	Calf given fecally-contaminated colostrum or milk (pasteurized, rehydrated or fresh)	Sterilise or disinfect equipment before first feed, regular clean feeding equipment between feeds. Pasteurise (to 71.7 °C for 15 seconds) to render oocysts non-viable (Harp et al. 1996). No specific type of artificial feeding mechanism (bucket, teat, tube, etc.) has higher risk (Brainard et al.2020).

APPENDIX 2

CHECKLIST FOR RECOMMENDED PRACTICES FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF CRYPTOSPORIDIOSIS

1/2

		Current practice	Change
Calving/birth	Are calves born in a pen never used for sick cows?		
	Is an additional layer of straw added before every calving or in case of a mat, is the mat cleaned between every calving to diminish the risk that the calf comes into contact with faeces or other contaminants?		
	Is the calf removed from the birth place as soon as possible?		
	Is the calving pen properly cleaned and disinfected at least once a year?		
Calves housing	Is there an optimal ventilation for the calves (if indoors: no drafts, but adequate air refreshments), if outdoors: hutches with the opening to south east to minimize the impact of the wind.		
	In case of hutches: are they placed logically to avoid spreading of germs between calves? (at least 0,5m between hutches, slurry and water cannot run off from one hutch to another)		
	Are the calves housed in a separate building from cows and older calves?		
	If calves are housed in groups, is there at least 1,5m ² floor area for each calf when younger than 1 month?		
	Is there enough individual housing to guarantee a sanitary empty period between calves of at least 1 week?		
	Is the knee test ok? (when you kneel in an individual calf pen, do your knees stay dry?)		
	Is the nest score adequate in individual housing (legs not visible when the calf lays down)?		
	Do you use calf jackets when it's colder than 10°C?		
	Is the access to the calf housing restricted to the calf carers or if other persons (ex. merchant) enter, is this with boots from the farm or is a clean foot bath used?		
	Are the hutches/pens, utensils and environment cleaned and disinfected between every calf that work against <i>Cryptosporidium</i> and other pathogens present on the farm, using an appropriate concentration/ protocol?		
Colostrum management	Is there a separate distribution system for water, food and milk available for each calf?		
	Is the surface of the pens/hutches so that it can be easily cleaned (smooth) and is the housing movable?		
	Do the dry cows get a ration with enough protein, minerals and vitamins?		
	Is the dry period at least 35 days?		
	Do the calves get good quality colostrum (22 brix at least)?		
	Do the calves get a quantity of colostrum adapted to the quality of the colostrum (Table 1) within 6 hours after birth?		
	Do the calves get a second colostrum intake within 12-24 hours after birth?		
Calf feeding	Do calves get colostrum with clean and regularly disinfected colostrum supply systems?		
	Do you use fresh colostrum from the own mother (or good quality colostrum from the colostrum bank if not possible)?		
	In case of whole milk, do you NOT use discarded milk?		

APPENDIX 2

CHECKLIST FOR RECOMMENDED PRACTICES FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF CRYPTOSPORIDIOSIS

2/2

		Current practice	Change
Calf feeding	Do you check the quality of the water used for preparing milk replacer and/or drinking water for calves at least once a year on its potability? (even if public water is used the waterpipes can be contaminated)		
	Do you feed on a high nutritional plan?		
	Are the calves provided with water, solid food within the first week of life?		
	Use of appropriate detergents and disinfectants for utensils		
Sick calves management	When in collective housing, are sick calves isolated?		
	Do you have a good rehydration plan for sick calves?		
	Do you use test kits or take samples to know which pathogen is responsible for the diarrhea?		
	Do you respect the sequence of treating calves (from young to old, healthy to sick)?		
Sanitary prevention - biosecurity	Do you use halofuginone lactate or paromomycin if an outbreak of <i>Cryptosporidium</i> has been confirmed?		
	Do you use vaccines against <i>E. coli</i> , rotavirus, coronavirus if these agents are responsible for calf diarrhea on the farm		

**BEST PRACTICES
FOR THE MANAGEMENT
OF CRYPTOSPORIDIOSIS
ON DAIRY FARMS**

